

Competing discourses on urban mobility in the context of climate change

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Abstract

In this work, we analyse the polarized debate about whether or not to restrict the use of private cars in the city of Barcelona, which took place between February 2023 and February 2024, a period in which municipal elections were held and the new city council was formed. We analyse, first, fragments of declarations, published in the local media, of two politicians from left-wing political parties, the current mayor, Jaume Collboni, from the Socialist Party (PSC), and the spokesperson of the main opposition party, En Comú, an environmentalist party. Secondly, the declarations of the spokesperson of a group of entrepreneurs in the city centre, who were opposed to any kind of restrictions on the use of cars, and those of two citizens' platforms in favour of a more sustainable city.

Using a methodology of Discourse Analysis, we describe the most important formal devices that show how two opposed cognitive frames are activated: the right to the unrestricted use of the car (based on the ontological metaphor “the car is a right”), as against the rights of citizens to have a more sustainable city (using lexical elements referring to the negative attributes of cars). The frame defended by the current mayor (the third) is nearer to the former, although he does formulate it in a more subtle and implicit way.

The work also includes a brief reflection on the differences between the discursive analysis of this type of discourse and the content analysis carried out by other social disciplines.

Keywords

Polarised conflicts; analysis of polarised discourse; analysis of environmental discourse; urban mobility; climate change denial; cognitive frame; ontological metaphor; (Critical) Discourse Analysis.

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Introduction

The need to reduce the emission of pollutants in the larger Spanish cities has, over recent years, turned into a discursive conflict between local authorities, environmentalists and the opponents of drastic steps being taken to reduce the use of private cars in cities. One of these cities is Barcelona, whose ex-mayor, Ada Colau, made green policies the main focus of her government during her eight-year term of office (2015–2023). At the same time, pressure groups in favour of the use of cars also arose.

In Morales-López and Floyd (2025), we analysed the discursive opposition to the elimination of public parking spaces from a group of residents in a working class area of Barcelona. In the present study we look further into this debate about the traditional use of the private car versus the defence of a new mobility in the city, with an analysis of the discourses around the time of the municipal elections (May 2023), and later on, after the make-up of the city council had been decided on; in all, from February 2023 to February 2024. The local elections were won by the Socialist candidate, Jaume Collboni, who defended a moderate stance on environmental issues related to mobility. We will analyse the statements on this topic made in the local media by him and his main opponent, both sharing a left-wing ideology, but also by a representative of the economic elite and by citizens organised in wealthier areas.

1. Theory and Methodology

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Our theoretical approach can be ascribed to Critical Discourse Analysis (or CDA) due to its emphasis on the relationship between discourses and power (Fairclough, 1989, 2001; van Dijk, 2003, 2009; Chilton, 2004; etc.), and to the constructivist contributions of Interactional Sociolinguistics (Gumperz, 1982) and of Cognitive Linguistics (Lakoff, 2004; Filardo-Llamas and Morales-López, 2022). For the present work, we feel it is useful to mention Fillmore's notion of "frame semantics" (1982: 111), as a complex way of looking at word meanings, and for gathering the meanings of lexical elements into the total meaning of the text. Thus, a frame, for him, refers to any system of concepts interrelated in such a way that to understand any one of them the whole structure is activated; when one of the items in such a structure is introduced into a text, all of the others are automatically made available.

Fillmore adds, moreover, that this term is synonymous with others used in the bibliography, such as "script", "scenario", "schema", "cognitive model", etc. Thus, he proposes that within the field of literal (semantic) meaning, the lexis used in a text or interaction automatically activates or refers to the context and the whole body of lexical items with which it shares the overall structure. In this way, the frame of the whole meaning is activated. If this is true in the case of the semantic meaning, it is much more so in that of the pragmatic and ideological meaning, as is the case which concerns us here.

At this point, it is necessary to connect the notion of frame with the theories of other authors: a) Goffman (1974: 10), for whom the frame is one of the basic conceptual forms that individuals activate in communication, and which guides them in its development. Goffman gave a social orientation to Bateson's (1972: 183, 193-194) notion of

a psychological frame, which the latter relates to a meta-communicative system (based on formal signals that guide the interpretation of messages). b) Lakoff’s cognitive proposal (2004); a frame is considered as an interpretative schema of experience shared by a social group, with persuasive goals. Thus, a frame is not just something activated in interaction by means of formal signs (as contextualisation cues, proposed by Gumperz, 1982), but potentially a more creative action. And c) Halliday’s (2014: 3) constructivist perspective, which emphasises above all the creative power of language and its ability to construct fresh meanings using an intentional selection from the whole group of available linguistic options (Payrató and Salvador, 2021; Filardo-Llamas and Morales-López, 2022: 4).

All of this means that, by means of discourses, speakers not only activate the contextual frameworks that guide them in interactions, but also construct new epistemologies or worldviews (cf. Slama-Cazacu, 1970: 240; Montesano Montessori, 2023; Pujante, 2024). For the philosopher of history Hayden White (1973), these alternative realities constitute different “narratives” of the same event, through the selection of creative formal resources. In this sense, the form is not merely an envelope for the function, but is also a constituent part of the overall meaning (White, 1987; Morales-López, 2019). This meaning is also completed in relation to the speaker’s subjectivity (emotional state, ethos), to the communicative functions (perspective of effects, pathos), and to the human action performed in the communication process. Cognition is therefore linked to discourse and to communicative activity, to concrete contexts and to intertextuality. From the viewpoint of Complexity Theory, the Chilean biologist Maturana (2006: 96) maintains that what makes us human is not language itself, but the act of communicating, as a social and cultural activity (see also Capra, 1996: 300; Blommaert and Varis, 2015).

On the specific theme of changes related to urban mobility, a review of the contemporary bibliography reveals that it has been the subject of attention from the point of view of Theory of Discourse and Content Analysis (Jacobs, 1999; Feindt and Oels, 2005; Doughty and Murray, 2016; Herdt, Skorstad and Mohus, 2022 and Muñoz Sanz, 2023), but less so from that of Critical Discourse Analysis (Caimotto, 2024; Filardo-Llamas and Pérez-Hernández, 2025). In other areas of environmental discourse, discourse analysts are more frequently present (Incelli, 2020; Deignan et al., 2019; and Salvador, 2022a, among others; see an update in Alcibar Cuello, 2023).

This shows that, in this environmental genre, as in others in general, discourse is a transdisciplinary notion, studied by different social science methodologies, including CDA. Some social researchers establish a radical difference with our discipline, but others carry out their research as an interdisciplinary task, reaping the benefits of a proper knowledge of discursive analysis for their own particular theoretical and applied purposes (see, for example Scollon, 2001, 2008). On the specific topic of climate change, Montesano Montessori (2020), Barlett and Montesano Montessori (2020), and Montesano Montessori (2023) include the CDA perspective in their content approach, orientated towards the analysis of the narratives and counter-narratives in competing discourses.

In our case, as critical discourse analysts, we need to pay close attention to the language choices made by speakers, following, in this way, Halliday’s (2014) premise of the form-function dialectic. In our discipline, what is important is not only to activate the meaning

transmitted in a particular discourse and context, but to detect what formal resources have been selected, from the most creative, such as metaphors and other rhetorical figures, to the most codified ones; what their frequency is, and novelties with regard to former discourses with a similar meaning, their difference from their opponents' discourse, etc. In such an analysis, what is relevant, then, is to consider meaning as a process (not as a product) constructed by these formal resources, in relation to its communicative functions and to the continuous activation and creation of the above-mentioned frames or narratives; that is, the different speakers' worldviews or perspectives to achieve certain actions in particular contexts related to power and ideologies (Morales-López, 2019).

As a methodology to be used in accordance with this systemic approach, we follow the linguistic ethnographic perspective, both in the selection of data and in the dialectic relationship between theory and analysis (Duranti, 1997; Scollon, 2001; Blommaert and Jie, 2010; Van der Aa and Blommaert, 2015). In the present study, the ethnographic method has enabled us to analyse the relevance of particular discourses within the local socio-political context of the city we are analysing, of its development during the last decades, and according to the political parties that have governed it. Likewise, these discourses are linked in with present-day debates about the climate crisis and the international "climate change denial" movement (Shi et al., 2020; Salvador, 2022a, b; Domínguez et al., 2022; Alcibar Cuello, 2023; Filardo-Llamas and Pérez-Hernández, 2025). It is only by joining together all of these perspectives that the meaning constructed in the data selected can be analysed, and later interpreted with a more comprehensive vision, as is explained below.

These data proceed from the following sources: different agents' declarations in the media, in their digital versions, published during 2023 and through to February 2024, whose main focus was the municipal elections in May 2023, and then the post-election period with the new municipal government. We have selected statements made by two left-wing politicians in the two major political parties at that time, as well as those of three citizens' organisations: on the one hand, the opinions of the Socialist candidate (PSC, Partit dels Socialistes de Catalunya) who is currently the mayor, Jaume Collboni, and of one of the opposition leaders, Janet Sanz, formerly responsible for the Environment and Town Planning during the years when Ada Colau was in charge of the municipal government; and, from the citizenry, declarations made by the spokesperson of a group of entrepreneurs, very much opposed to Ada Colau's environmental policy, and by two citizens' platforms who are in favour of such a policy. All the statements quoted refer to the subject of mobility in the city of Barcelona.

Since more than a decade ago, we have been carrying out ethnographic research in Barcelona, ever since the emergence of the social movement known as "15M", of which the ex-mayor Ada Colau was a prominent leader. She was an activist who became a local politician, using these citizens' platforms. We have researched them since they arose, as a result of the economic crisis of 2008 (Montesano Montessori and Morales-López, 2015; Morales-López, 2016, 2017). During Ada Colau's two terms as mayor of Barcelona, her political agenda (and that of her political group at that time *En Comú-Podem*) was based predominantly on the redistribution of wealth in benefit of working class districts. At the same time, she began to promote great changes in favour of a greener city with more room for pedestrians, on the premise that environmental degradation would affect citizens' everyday lives.

Her political aim was to thus create a new design of the city, so as to improve the everyday life of its residents, rather than one for the exclusive benefit of wealthy neo-liberal elites. Indeed, she was elected to serve as mayor after four years of Xavier Trias’s conservative government (2011-2015). The latter, in turn, had taken over as mayor after different Socialist governments had exercised power for years, (the most important being that of Pasqual Maragall, who was mayor between 1982 and 1997). While Trias proposed the transformation of Barcelona into a city serving the interests of the entrepreneurial class (in fact, his slogan was ‘Barcelona, Smart City’, focusing on the technology industry), Colau changed the meaning of the adjective “smart” into an attribute of citizens who were able to construct collective intelligence through cooperation with each other in each of the different districts (Molpeceres, 2017; Montesano Montessori, 2020).

Her environmental project, specifically based on more space for residents, was challenged by the entrepreneurial groups, who accused Ada Colau of hindering the use of private cars, and, thus, going against the city’s economic interests. The political opposition managed to convince the city’s working classes and so Ada Colau lost the municipal elections, albeit narrowly (Morales-López and Floyd, 2025). The issue of urban mobility was a prominent one in the above-mentioned electoral campaign in 2023, and continued to be so in the following months, as we will show below in the data selected. In this debate, the Socialist candidate Collboni designed his opposition to Colau by making an alliance with the economic pressure groups within the city.

Actually, what is seen in the data selected is not merely a dispute between the discourses of opposing groups, but a debate which we believe needs to be analysed in connection with actions (see also Scollon, 2001, 2008), in this case, linked in with different power groups and the potential actions needed to transform the city’s economy. The continual interaction between these data and the wider socio-political context, as the ethnographic perspective proposes, is fundamental to a better understanding of this conflict concerning mobility, and relates it to political and entrepreneurial actions and counter-actions.

Our purpose in this research paper is twofold: (1) An analysis of how mobility, in particular related to the private car, is referred to in the data; which formal resources (linguistic, pragmatic and/or argumentative) have been used to express it, and the relationship with terms such as pollution, health and/or the redesign of urban spaces. (2) A description of the different frames that are activated in these discourses, the degree of conflict among them and their relationship to actions.

2. Analysis and Results

The analysis will adopt the following schema: (a) the declarations of Jaume Collboni, the then-candidate of the Socialist Party; (b) the counterargument of Janet Sanz, as spokesperson of En Comú, in the opposition; (c) from the citizenry, declarations made by the spokesperson of a group of enterprises and (d) by two citizens’ platforms.

2.1. The opinions of Jaume Collboni

In the first place, we have chosen the opinion expressed by Mr. Collboni as a response to the problem of the pollution caused by private cars, in an interview prior to the election, as the Socialist Party candidate. We must recall that this party has played a very important role in the city's politics, governing it during most of the time since democracy was reinstated in Spain. Having lost the city hall between 2011 and 2023, they recovered it after beating Ada Colau in these elections. The question of whether or not to restrict the use of private cars was one of the key issues used by Collboni against his opponent, and he was questioned on the subject, as follows:

(1) Journalist: What will the PSC do to reduce the pollution caused by private vehicles?

Collboni: Electrify the city. We are the leading city in Spain when it comes to public charging points for cars. Apart from that, we are always working alongside the automobile industry, and the automobile sector as a whole, when they make a huge effort, as in the case of SEAT, to manufacture electric vehicles. To stress this point further, I believe it is a mistake to wage war on cars, because much of individual mobility is out of pure necessity. There are many people who, in order to commute to the industrial estates in Montcada or Baix Llobregat, but who live in El Clot, have no choice but to take their car. They would love to be able to choose the train or use the subway, but we cannot invent a world that simply does not exist. We have to make every effort to speed up the process of decarbonisation of mobility in the city.

J: But do you believe that the cities of the future will be free of cars? You have already stated that you will limit the “superilla”, which has earned international recognition.³

C: I want such recognition to be on the part of the residents of Barcelona, so that they understand what is being done by the city council, so that they understand that their way of life is not being threatened by dogmatic stances. I want to stress that nobody wants to be stuck in a tailback full of pollution, and that, if they are, it is because they are unable to afford an electric car, and because there is no alternative in the public transport system.⁴

The journalist's question activates the ecological agenda, referring to the topic of mobility in connection with the city's high levels of pollution: “...the pollution caused by private vehicles”. In his response, Collboni activates his own frame, in which the car does not receive this negative attribute: the use of the nominal expression “electric vehicles” linked to actions “electrify the city...” and “speed up the process of decarbonisation” present his sustainable option for the future; he adds, too, an argument based on an

³ The journalist is referring to the superblock or *superilla of Consell de Cent Street*, the process of making this street in the Eixample district more peaceful, with fewer cars and more green zones.

⁴ Downloaded from the following website: <https://elpais.com/espana/catalunya/2023-02-12/collboni-la-guerra-contra-el-coche-es-un-error-mucha-de-la-movilidad-individual-no-tiene-alternativa.html>

example: an electric car “manufactured by SEAT”, the firm based in the Barcelona metropolitan area.

These positive characteristics of the automobile (electric cars, decarbonisation and local manufacturing), could be considered as a self-defence strategy, prior to the expression of his opinion in the next statements. We highlight the following formal resources:

a) Two lexicalised ontological metaphors (Lakoff and Johnson, 1980): “a mistake to wage war on cars” and “we cannot invent a world that simply does not exist”. In the first, the car (the target domain) is identified as a target in a war (the source domain); and in the second his opponent’s political world (the target domain) is presented as a gadget created by an inventor (the source domain). These two metaphors transform his political opponent’s proposal into something more tangible, in order to, in this way, demonstrate more easily that it is unattainable.

(b) A causal argument to vindicate the necessity of mobility for the working people who commute to the industrial estates and who cannot move around on public transport: “... because much of individual mobility is out of pure necessity”.

From the theory of argumentation, these latter resources can be considered, too, as an argument which functions as one of the types called “common places”. Common places are arguments constructed as unquestionable in our community (Perelman and Olbrechts-Tyteca 1958, and Perelman 1997: 44). One of their types is the “common place of the current state of affairs” (“le lieu de l’existant”), defined by these authors as the defence of the current state of things, the prevailing situation, what is real, as against what is possible or impossible; in Collboni’s speech, it is formulated in contrast to his opponent’s solutions, which, he argues, are unrealisable.

The journalist next addresses the issue of whether or not Collboni feels it is necessary to reduce the number of cars in the city in order to lower pollution levels, as his political opponent did. Collboni avoids answering the question directly, insisting that electric cars will be the answer when people find them more economically accessible. In this interview, his aim seems to be to present himself as the defender of working class interests, by means of causal arguments (“because... because...”) trying to justify their need to use private cars.

Thus, with all the discursive resources, the frame activated is the defence of cars, although they should be more and more ecological: present-day cars will be substituted by their electric counterparts in the future, when local manufacturing technology makes this feasible and accessible to the working classes. He contemplates neither a reduction in the use of cars nor an improvement in public transportation (as Ada Colau did with the extension of the tram lines), as his electric car proposal in the future will not involve polluting substances.

One month later, in another newspaper article, he made further declarations:

(2) Collboni has declared that his speech “is a great chance to contrast” the two models. “There exists a very ‘anti-car’ position, but we do not share it. There are two alternatives to go green. Consell de Cent may have a positive short-term outcome,⁵ but to extend it to the whole of Eixample is just not viable, and the economic costs are too high”, he says. Some months ago, Collboni announced, over breakfast with the media, that if he were mayor he would “halt and make an evaluation of” the number of streets involved in the “pacification” of Eixample; at the same time, he made public his intention to continue with the rehabilitation of the interiors of blocks, a process begun by Socialist Party mayors 20 years ago.

[...] Collboni expressed his regret that during the last three terms of office (12 years) no effort had been made to take back the new interiors of blocks of buildings [...] “Priorities have changed over the years; now the focus is on the road network, while in fact [transforming] the interior of blocks has less impact on the economy, is less costly, has less negative side effects and is risk-free”, the candidate stated.⁶

As against Ada Colau’s model of pedestrianising parts of some streets, creating carless *superillas* (the Spanish term; in Catalan *superilles*), with the aim of increasing the city’s green areas, Collboni proposes retrieving an idea of previous Socialist mayors: recovering the interior spaces of blocks of buildings, which are commonly used as storage space. Though it may seem in fact an economically more expensive option for the city budget, he defends it by a “pragmatic argument” (Perelman and Olbrechts-Tyteca, 1958); that is, it will have positive economic effects for private companies: “has less impact on the economy, is less costly, has less negative side effects and is risk-free”. So, as far as Collboni is concerned, the option is that of the streets for cars and green zones for residents on the insides of blocks of buildings; with the *superillas*, the number of cars needs to be reduced so that some streets can be converted into green zones. Again, Collboni affirms that cars have a positive role to play in maintaining the city’s economic activity, as against the “anti-car” (environmentalist) discourse expressed by his main opponent.

Collboni is implicitly aligning himself with those sectors which explicitly argued that people had a vested right to use cars in the city, as we will see below when referring to the spokesperson of the business group “Barcelona Oberta”. In Morales-López and Floyd (2025), we described this position by way of the ontological metaphor “the car as a right” (mentioned as well in Doughty and Murray, 2016).

2.2. The opinions of the “En Comú” party spokesperson

Janet Sanz, from the political group of the ex-mayor Ada Colau, opposes Collboni’s proposal to prioritise the retrieval of the interiors of blocks of buildings instead of green zones in the streets. The following is one of her declarations, made in February 2024, after the controversy sparked by a court ruling against a *superilla*, which we will refer to in the next section:

⁵ He alludes to the *superilla of Consell de Cent Street*, mentioned above.

⁶ <https://elpais.com/espana/catalunya/2023-03-22/collboni-apuesta-por-recuperar-30-interiores-de-manzana-como-alternativa-a-la-superilla-inviabile-de-colau.html>

(3) “The *superilles* generate walking spaces”, states the ex-deputy mayor, who was at the same time responsible for town planning, Janet Sanz [...] “The *superilles* and the recuperation of the interiors of blocks are compatible, but neither the speed of execution of the work nor the price are comparable”, she states. Furthermore, she stresses that her solution “would be an answer to [the car as] a perversion of the twentieth century, a product of speculation”, while the other alternative attends to “a problem of pollution and public health, as well as of the fair distribution of public space, which we need to address.”⁷

Janet Sanz’s speech functions as a counter-argument, in contrast to the current mayor’s position: her point of view regarding cars contrasts with Collboni’s positive view expressed above. Rather than seeing the car as a positive article in economic terms, and essential for the working classes, Janet Sanz refers to “walking spaces” as the contrasting type of solution; the car is described, lexically, in the following terms: “perversion of the twentieth century”, “a product of speculation”, “pollution and public health”, and is contrasted with “the fair distribution of public space”.

Therefore, a different frame is activated, in which there are options other than a mobility that involves the car: mobility on foot. In fact, these lexical expressions can be analysed as metonymies of capitalism. Instead of explicitly mentioning the latter, she does its consequences: the car as a negative effect of capitalist business people’s decisions (“perversion”, “speculation”); also, the cause: “pollution and public health (problems)”. Furthermore, in this frame, the car and the space given over to it are not a right (the metaphor mentioned above), as is inferred from the use of the lexical expression “the fair distribution of public space”. With the expression “walking spaces” she calls for policies to redress the balance within this space (in fact, cars occupy about 70% of the urban space in Barcelona).

2.3. The declarations of the spokesperson of the business group “Barcelona Oberta” and a residents’ association

Firstly, we will analyse the opinions expressed by Gabriel Jené, the spokesman of a group of entrepreneurs with interests in one of the central, middle class areas of the city: the Eixample (one of the most popular districts with tourists, because of its Art Nouveau architecture). This group was totally against the green zone that Ada Colau placed in Consell de Cent Street, and they brought the case to court; the sentence, delivered in September 2023, found in their favour, to the extent that it obliged the public works to be revoked and the area returned to its former state. After the controversy provoked by this ruling, Gabriel Jené issued the following statement (September 2023):

(4) (a) Jené has stated that he is not against changes in Barcelona, but calls for dialogue. “We understand that the solution to this problem is not that of building workers”, Jené says, underlining the fact that the retail traders he represents are not “climate change deniers”... What Barcelona Oberta wants ... is that cars should not be “criminalised”,

⁷ https://nacioidigital.cat/impacte/ciutats/entre-superilles-i-interiors-dilla-les-claus-i-el-preu-dels-canvis-urbanistics-a-barcelona_1821921_102.html

and that they should consider the possibility that the traffic of vehicles be “guaranteed access” to the city centre [...]”⁸

(b) “We are not climate change deniers... we want access ...we don’t want more cars, simply that cars should be able to get where they need to ...”⁹

As a justification for having taken their opposition to the scheme to court, where the sentence obliged the city council to undo the public work completed, (in 4a), in (4b), he constructs a “disclaimer” (van Dijk 2003: 64, 73-74; 2009), an argument which in its implicit structure seems a fallacy, as in the first part it denies what is affirmed in the second part: “we are not climate change deniers [but] vehicle traffic [should] be ‘guaranteed access’ to the city centre.” As for the words used, he activates the metaphor of the “car as a right”: “not criminalise” the car, and “guarantee access” for traffic to reach the centre. With the use of this second statement, cars are perceived as having rights, with unrestricted mobility in public spaces, exactly the opposite opinion to that of Janet Sanz (Example 3). The difference with regard to Collboni is that Gabriel Jené’s frame is that of cars in general, without attributes, not electric vehicles; therefore, Jené’s reference is made to the current fleet of vehicles, of which only the oldest and those which contaminate most are banned from city centres.

Residents of the existing green zone, organised under the name “Eixample Respira” (Eixample Breathes), criticised Jené’s declarations in the following way (September 2023):

(5) The residents associations [FAVB] will oppose the court sentence and will call for the Council to file an appeal. In their view, the balance between car users and pedestrians needs to be corrected, and they accuse certain economic sectors, who “in their fight against political power” are contesting all municipal decisions in court. The FAVB accuse Barcelona Oberta of punishing the population via the courts. The residents’ association Eixample Respira issues a statement in which it regrets the sentence, which “goes against pacification”, and where “mobility in pollutant private vehicles is made a priority over and above public health”.¹⁰

As the residents’ association’s very name suggests, they express their opposition to “Barcelona Oberta”, in which they again activate the negative frame for the car: the need for “the balance... of public space” (a synonymous expression to “the fair distribution of public space” used in 3). And the use of words and phrases whereby they provide evidence that cars are harmful to the city: “Barcelona Oberta” (the business’ association) wants to “punish the population” as against the “pacification” of the different areas of the city (that is to say pedestrianisation), and the “pollutant private vehicles” over “public health”.

⁸ https://es.ara.cat/sociedad/barcelona/impulsores-recurso-superilla-no-queremos-revertir-obras-consell-cent_1_4795941.html

⁹ Gabriel Jené’s intervention on the local TV: <https://beteve.cat/economia/barcelona-oberta-no-vol-execucio-sentencia-consell-cent-2/>

¹⁰ <https://www.elpuntavui.cat/societat/article/6-urbanisme/2331794-revertir-el-carrer-podria-ser-traumatic.html>

2.4. An organised residents’ response in favour of a bicycle lane in an upper class area

In similar terms to those of “Eixample Respira”, a second group of residents carries out a demonstration, this time in an upper class area (the district of Sarrià), in favour of a bicycle lane built by the previous municipal government, which had also been criticised by certain sectors. Mayor Collboni, once elected, had made public his intention to draw up a report to assess the impact and use of this cycle lane. We here present residents’ opinions in the following example (October 2023):

(6) 500 cyclists defend the cycle lane in the Via Augusta in Barcelona: “Don’t touch it!”

The route [of the bicycle lane], which communicates upper class districts in the more elevated side of the city has become symbolic, due to the fear that it might be dismantled by the new city council.

[...] A manifesto drawn up by the different groups was read out, calling on the municipal council to “drop any possible action that might overturn or modify it”; they offer to take part in the evaluation of the infrastructure, and urge residents to “celebrate the fact that the bicycle lane exists, use it and fill it with bikes”.

The text reminds people that Barcelona exceeds the WHO’s recommended levels of contamination, and claims that “a current of opinion against the bicycle lane has been artificially created, which reflects the fact that public transport in the area is unprofitable, and the success of some pressure groups in their attempt to maintain pollutant motor traffic in the city centre... Does Barcelona really wish to join the group of cities that deny the harmful effects of traffic on our health, and the climate emergency?” asks the manifesto, in reference to those cities that have dismantled infrastructures for bicycles.¹¹

In line with these opinions, bicycles are proposed as an alternative to cars; therefore, “Eixample respira” is no longer defending a type of car, as in Collboni’s frame, but another hyponymic category related to mobility: the bicycle. Also the lexical expressions “pollutant traffic” and “harmful effects of traffic...”, highlight the negative consequences of the use of cars in the city. The declaration refers as well to the social actors responsible for this situation: “some pressure groups”, as a kind of lobby in the district. And as opposed to this group’s power, the text adds an argument of authority (the reference to WHO data about pollution in the city) and a rhetorical question as a strategy to discredit this opposition group, which is described as being composed of climate change deniers (“deny the harmful effects of traffic on our health, and the climate emergency”).

¹¹ <https://elpais.com/espana/catalunya/2023-10-21/unos-500-ciclistas-reivindican-el-carril-bici-de-la-via-augusta-de-barcelona-no-se-toca.html>

2.5. Results: The different frames of interpretation

The frame that emerges from Collboni's discourse implicitly recognises the problem of climate change and the need to propose solutions, but it is related to the future: electric cars, their manufacturing process and electrification. At present, the use of cars remains unquestioned (implicitly he is activating the metaphor "the car as a right"), and their use can co-exist with certain measures for sustainability, for example, rehabilitating the interiors of blocks of buildings, to convert them into green spaces. In this aspect, his proposal is not in fact anything new. This was an idea of previous Socialist mayors, with the aim of reconciling the then growing demand for cars with the great density of population within the city (wedged into a narrow space between the mountains and the sea); thus far, these measures have been unable to transform the model of mobility in order to reduce the high levels of pollution within the city.

Collboni reaffirms his model for the city when he uses the metaphors "not wage war on cars" and "we cannot invent a world that simply does not exist", and he alludes to lexical items that refer to dogmatism ("anti", "dogmatic positions"). These metaphors and lexical items show how Collboni activates a more moderate frame in terms of mobility, by which he tries to achieve two communicative functions. On the one hand, a sharing of identification with different social groups in the city; with some economic elites in the middle and upper-middle class districts (in competition with the right-wing parties; one of them Trias's party, alluded to above) and also identification with the workers in lower-middle class areas (plumbers, painters, etc.) who move around the city by car and were traditionally the main source of votes for the Socialist Party in the metropolitan area of Barcelona. On the other hand, self-legitimising, in order to reinforce and consolidate his ideological position in relation to his main political opponent sharing a left-wing ideology, the ex-mayor Ada Colau, whom he beat in the municipal elections, but by a relatively small margin.

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The second frame reveals the environmentalist ideology of, on the one hand, the representative of Colau's political group, and, on the other, citizens' groups who have begun to defend a greener city, with more sustainable means of transport. In their discursive resources, they underline the negative characteristics of cars, in order to link this in with the capitalist past (developmentalism) with its negative consequences for residents' health. In this way, this capitalist model is contrasted with their green proposal for the city, represented by the "superillas", "pacification" (pedestrianisation) and more bicycle lanes. That is, more space for living, as explained by Filardo-Llamas and Pérez-Hernández (2025: 114).

This second frame opposes the city's economic elites as well. The latter activates the third frame, as defended by "Barcelona Oberta"; this group occupies the same middle- and upper middle class areas as the two above-mentioned groups of citizens. The economic elites seem to be more in favour of Collboni's discourse, due to his defence of the car. The words used by the spokesperson of "Barcelona Oberta" are thus displayed as an example of a business-as-usual discourse, in ecological terms: he defends the use of cars through the metaphor "the car as a right" in order to delegitimise environmentalism as being opposed to progress (Salvador 2022a, b), even by using the law courts as is the case here. However, the most outstanding discursive resource used by Gabriel Jené is the disclaimer, which seems to be used to defend himself from the criticism received.

Overall, three different frames or narratives have been observed, constructed by diverse discursive resources used by the different participants. These discourses were delivered during a specific period of time, that of the municipal elections and the formation of the new government which followed them. The subject of mobility, with arguments in favour of and against the traditional predominant use of the private car, reveal that it was presented as a polarised debate by the two parties analysed, both on the political left, the Socialist Party and En Comú; this was clearly based on a power struggle (Chilton, 2004: 3). Competition between these two led them both to lose the elections; the winner was the right-wing nationalist party Junts per Catalunya, whose candidate was again Xavier Trias. However, En Comú (which finished third) chose to support Collboni as mayor and prevent the right-wing party from governing in the city.¹²

This discursive polarisation on the issue of mobility demonstrates the lack of consensus about the design of the city against the backdrop of the challenge posed by climate change. The eight year period during which Ada Colau governed meant an important step forward in environmentalism, demonstrating that social action by traditional left-wing parties at the present time is entirely compatible with policies that defend the environment. However, the bitter opposition shown by economic interests against a change in mobility policies also found an echo in the working classes, so En Comú ended up losing power (see in this respect Morales-López and Floyd, 2025). The support received by ecology-conscious residents in wealthy areas of the city (as was shown in our analysis) was insufficient to keep En Comú in power. The electorate showed that it was not prepared for such radical changes in environmental matters, and thus their votes went to more moderate and conservative positions.

Collboni and his team realised this, as is shown by the more conservative frame constructed in favour of the private car. Using this political strategy, his party was able to win back the support of residents in the city’s working class areas, and thus take back power. It was also helped, as already mentioned, by a practical decision taken by Ada Colau’s party in favour of political consensus. In this new phase of government, Collboni has been reliant on En Comú for the day-to-day management of the city’s affairs, so possibly certain environmental projects will be kept, which will benefit both residents and the transformation of the city in a more sustainable way. For example, on the matter of public transport, it may be possible to resume En Comú’s project concerning the continuation of work on the tramway, thus enabling fresh direct connections between different areas of the city.

As a final consideration, what is seen is that, in the frame constructed by Collboni, the lack of creativity within his own political party is evident when it comes to designing the city in the face of the challenge of climate change. Likewise, as for the discourse strategy used by En Comú, it might be worthwhile emphasising the fact that the transformations needed to make the city more ecologically viable must first be inculcated into its residents, especially in working class neighbourhoods, in order to gain their support. In the present article, the agreements reached with residents of wealthier areas is underlined, but, as seen

¹² <https://www.lavanguardia.com/elecciones/municipales-2023/cataluna/barcelona/barcelona/> <https://www.elperiodico.com/es/barcelona/20230529/resultado-elecciones-barcelona-2023-ganado-28m-87823358/> / <https://www.publico.es/politica/collboni-elegido-alcalde-barcelona-votos-comuns-pp.html>

in Morales-López and Floyd (2025), the direct opposition shown by groups of residents of a working-class area was very significant.

Conclusion

In this article, we have presented a systematic discourse analysis of a series of conflicting discourses centred on mobility in the city of Barcelona. This analysis has shown how the conflict developed concerning the design of the city with regard to mobility, and whether or not the private car is to be considered an acquired right obtained by citizens. The main formal resources we highlight are the metaphor “the car as a right”, activated implicitly by the current mayor and explicitly by the spokesperson of the group of entrepreneurs, as opposed to the lexical expressions that function as metonymies (attributes and effects of capitalism: perversion, speculation, and the cause of pollution and health problems), used by En Comú and by the two citizens’ platforms mentioned. With these main resources, our analysis has demonstrated that three different frames or narratives are activated, two of them being completely antagonistic: that of the traditional status quo, with unrestricted use of the car to reach the city centre, and the opposing one in favour of a transformation of the city towards an ecologically friendly model. The frame constructed by the present mayor, Collboni, is that of implicit support for the former frame, claiming that his main political rival is dogmatic on the subject of the use of private vehicles; at the same time, he creates a strategy whereby he apparently sides with environmentalism, when he explicitly alludes to the sustainable future of the city by means of the use of electric vehicles. This is in fact a discursive ambiguity by which he makes no commitment at all on this subject, but whereby he hopes to attract the votes of citizens unhappy with the ecological projects set in motion by Ada Colau. This ambiguity turned out to be a successful strategy, as is shown by the fact that he is now the mayor of Barcelona.

From a theoretical/methodological viewpoint, we have referred to the difference between our own perspective and that of other social scientists, whose aim is the analysis of the contents of these discourses. Critical discourse analysis demonstrates that the construction of meaning is intimately related to the specific choice of discursive forms (both denotative constructions and those that activate implicit meaning). Thereby, specific reference is made at some length of the different actors, their relationship with ideologies, the (local or global, etc) context, intertextuality, and so on. We believe that thus we are better placed to study the processes of meaning construction in the analysis of any particular discursive genre.

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